

NUTRITION STUDIES IN BIHAR. PART II. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOME LOCAL EDIBLES.

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Forty local edibles were analysed chemically as to the moisture, fat, crude fibre, carbohydrate, calcium, phosphorus and iron content. The methods recommended by the American Agriculturists Association were followed during analysis with slight modification. Of the cereal grains *marooa* is the richest source of calcium. The various *sattoos* contain fairly high percentage of proteins and minerals. Rice and wheat bran contain protective dietary elements in abundance. *Gurh* is rich in calcium.

About a year ago, the intergovernmental conference of the League of Nations (*Report of Intergovernmental Conference*, No. A., 19, 1937, III, 69) observed "In various countries a considerable amount of work has been carried out on the nutritive value of foodstuff. The importance of extending and completing investigations of this nature is pointed out". Ranganathan *et al* (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 689) worked out the proximate chemical composition of 200 Indian foods, but out of this comprehensive list only three items were obtained from this province (Darbhanga). During diet survey operations in the province by the author (*Patna J. Med.*, XIV, 1) a need was felt for figures giving the nutritive value of foodstuffs consumed locally. An effort has been made to assess chemically the nutritive value of those local foods which have not so far been analysed at other laboratories in India. The results of investigation of forty items of food are presented in this paper. The methods of analysis were the same as described by Ranganathan *et al* (*loc. cit.*). The list includes 29 kinds of grain foods, 5 kinds of leafy vegetables, 10 kinds of other vegetables, 3 kinds of fish and 2 miscellaneous foods, all purchased from different markets in the city of Patna.

Some of the items of food need explaining. "Besam Boont" is nothing except flour made from dried Bengal gram sold in the market; on the other hand "Boont Sattoo" is the flour made from roasted or baked Bengal gram. Other *sattoos* (consumed mostly in the rural area) are prepared from the respective pulses or cereals in the same way. "Suthni" is a root vegetable, which is either boiled and eaten as such or dried and flour made out of it for cakes. This food is not popular with the upper classes. "Tilouri" often makes a palatable dish and is prepared by soaking certain pulse grains mostly black gram (or urid), grinding them to a paste and drying them up in small bits,

Table of Food Values.

Name of food. stuff.	Botanical name	Moisture.	Protein.	Fat (ether extractives)	Mineral matters.	Carbohydrate.	Crude fibre.	Calcium	Phosphorus.	Iron (in mg.).	Caloric value per 100 g (calculated).	Remarks.
1. Kalandan rice	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	10.47%	6.09%	0.23%	0.56%	22.65%	...	0.003%	0.120%	2.50%	366.0	Raw milled.
2. Ramsal rice	"	11.00	7.40	0.75	1.12	79.73	...	0.006	0.170	3.00	364.2	Parboiled.
3. Basmati rice	"	10.01	6.63	0.33	0.71	82.32	...	0.003	0.121	2.55	367.8	Raw milled.
4. Samjira rice	"	10.33	7.03	0.15	0.74	81.75	...	0.002	0.130	2.73	365.4	"
5. Whole wheat flour.	<i>Triticum vulgare</i>	12.58	12.77	2.40	2.21	68.88	1.16	0.060	0.319	6.32	357.1	
6. Maroia	<i>Elousine coracina</i>	10.88	6.12	1.97	2.05	78.47	0.49	0.301	0.216	4.20	365.2	
7. Water chestnut flour	<i>Trapa bispinosa</i>	11.61	10.23	3.22	2.94	71.00	...	0.082	0.424	3.00	367.1	
8. Puffed maize	<i>Zea mays</i>	7.35	9.24	4.78	1.92	74.59	2.12	0.005	0.322	37.50	388.6	
9. Puffed paddy (Laos)	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	10.49	8.41	4.74	1.14	69.83	5.39	0.006	0.210	4.62	364.9	
10. Rice bran	"	14.79	19.06	12.28	16.65	28.31	8.04	0.136	2.844	111.42	308.1	
11. Wheat bran	<i>Triticum vulgare</i>	16.78	13.81	3.95	6.04	55.55	9.87	0.118	1.394	15.00	321.1	
12. Moong dal or green gram	<i>Phaseolus radiatus</i>	9.91	24.29	0.91	3.15	61.78	..	0.029	0.373	4.80	361.2	Without outer husk.

Table of Food Values (contd.).

Name of food stuff.	Botanical name.	Moisture.	Protein	Fat (ether extractive).	Mineral matters.	Carbohydrate.	Grode fibre.	Calcium.	Phosphorus.	Iron (in mg.).	Caloric value per 100 g. (calculated).
13. Besam boont	<i>Cicer arctinum</i>	12.20%	23.88%	5.45%	2.34%	53.01%	1.12%	0.044%	0.316%	6.32%	374.1
14. Boont sattoo	"	14.12	20.36	7.20	2.50	54.54	1.26	0.065	0.318	8.57	374.1
15. Makal sattoo	<i>Zea mays</i>	11.44	9.32	3.55	1.82	71.97	1.61	0.000	0.259	6.31	366.3
16. Jao sattoo	<i>Hordium vulgare</i>	14.99	12.00	2.37	5.12	67.69	1.17	0.033	0.419	0.00	347.3
17. Matar sattoo	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	11.18	25.43	1.52	2.20	38.81	1.06	0.000	0.298	5.06	358.7
18. Soojee	<i>Sambolus</i>	9.28	9.05	0.95	0.95	80.16	...	0.040	0.151	4.00	374.6
19. Sewai or wheat flour fine rolls	<i>Trichium vulgare</i>	10.91	10.94	0.44	0.64	77.07	...	0.029	0.201	2.22	364.9
20. Kachri or tender Bengal gram	<i>Cicer arctinum</i>	83.58	5.53	0.14	0.84	9.61	...	0.050	0.113	1.80	64.6
LEAFY VEGETABLES											
21. Pooin sag	<i>Basselia rubra</i>	93.14	2.69	0.19	1.26	1.75	0.97	0.086	0.086	27.59	20.0
22. Lal sag	<i>Amaranthus blitum</i>	88.40	2.64	0.20	2.02	5.59	0.85	0.120	0.073	18.18	30.8
23. Pakki sag	<i>Spinacea oleracea</i>	91.59	1.80	0.21	1.05	4.53	0.82	0.212	0.082	22.34	27.9
24. Boont sag	<i>Cicer arctinum</i>	87.97	2.76	0.81	2.46	5.35	0.95	0.172	0.260	22.69	40.8
25. Khenari sag	<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>	89.00	3.29	0.65	1.20	5.24	0.72	0.310	0.108	4.36	41.0

Table of Food Values (contd.).

Name of food stuff.	Botanical name.	Moisture.	Protein.	Fat (ether ex- tractives)	Mineral matter.	Carbohydrate.	Crude fibre.	Calcium.	Phosphorus.	Iron (in mg.).	Caloric value per 100 g. (calculated).	Remarks.
Other Vegetables												
26. Parwar or Pato	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	91.00%	1.73%	0.30%	0.50%	4.13%	2.11%	0.086%	0.080%	0.56%	27.7	
27. Kandri (Telakmocho)	<i>Cephalandra indica</i>	96.23	1.78	0.15	0.43	0.78	5.9	0.020	0.047	0.68	11.9	
28. Khekas or Chithail Kankrol	<i>Momordica charantia</i> <i>chinensis</i>	84.09	2.61	0.66	1.02	5.69	5.63	0.021	0.14	2.59	40.2	
29. Kadam	<i>Antisecephalus cadamba</i>	82.11	1.42	0.12	0.96	15.39	"	0.081	0.067	1.61	70.0	
30. Suthni		75.89	3.94	0.23	1.02	28.13	0.79	0.021	0.084	0.75	95.6	With skin.
31. Arui	<i>Colocasia antiquorum</i>	75.24	2.55	0.10	1.12	20.32	0.49	0.020	0.091	0.79	94.7	
32. Nenna	<i>Luffa aegyptia</i>	93.66	1.41	0.07	0.40	3.58	0.88	0.018	0.050	0.49	21.1	
33. Barsama (Makhan seem).	<i>Cannavalia gladiata</i>	84.21	2.26	0.22	0.76	11.59	1.02	0.086	0.057	0.73	58.6	
34. Seem or Broad bean	<i>Dolichos lablab</i>	86.43	2.90	0.24	0.88	7.57	1.98	0.091	0.089	1.20	45.2	
35. Kankri	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	93.73	0.84	0.10	0.50	4.10	0.73	0.028	0.049	0.94	21.2	
FISH												
36. Rebu Fish	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	78.09	17.82	2.77	1.32	"	"	0.090	0.277	0.62	98.8	
37. Bachwa Fish	<i>Clupeoma garna</i>	76.37	28.13	4.40	1.10	"	"	0.062	0.223	0.53	115.2	
38. Bhoona Fish (chittal)		77.30	17.56	3.70	1.44	"	"	0.082	0.281	0.72	97.1	
Miscellaneous												
39. Gurh		8.86	0.23	0.03	1.00	89.84	"	0.400	0.045	7.06	369.8	
40. Tilsonri		12.23	21.81	0.96	3.12	61.88	"	0.174	0.389	2.35	332.1	

DISCUSSION.

Of the four varieties of local rice analysed the mineral content (as also calcium and phosphorus) was found comparatively high in Ramsal, which is nothing other than parboiled Basmati grains. Amongst the cereal grains "Marooa" was found to be richer in the most important mineral element calcium. Unfortunately this food grain is associated with social taboo and as such is rarely used by the middle classes. Only very poor people, mostly of the lower castes, make flour out of this grain for unleavened cakes and consume them as such. If only the people in the lower middle classes could be persuaded to use marooa flour for milk porridge, the same would serve as a cheap and nutritive breakfast for children. Puffed paddy is also comparatively rich in mineral salts.

Except the *makai*, other sattoas have got very high protein and mineral content, the calcium yield is also fairly moderate; thus sattoos form a highly nutritive, easily portable and ready-made group of edibles. These powdered grain foods need only water to make them into a dough, which with a pinch of salt and green chillies makes an excellent and wholesome repast on occasions when cooking becomes inconvenient or impossible.

All the five types of leafy vegetables examined show fairly high calcium values. The first three in the list are consumed only after cooking, but the last two ("Boont and Khesari sāg") are consumed in a raw state when the plants are still very tender. With the growth of urbanisation this healthy practice is becoming unpopular, if not obsolete. "Gurh" was found to contain an unusually high percentage of calcium, this was evidently due to the fact that during the process of manufacture, the thickened and highly coloured juice of sugar cane is treated with lime for clarification. Calcium of the lime is retained in Gurh to a very large extent. From the point of view of nutrition the superiority of Gurh over sugar can hardly be overrated.

Rice and wheat brans (polishings) are used exclusively as cattle fodder, though they contain all the proximate principles of food and mineral elements in very large proportions. The protein content of the rice bran was found to be particularly high (19.06 %) and it stands to reason that if these polishings be utilised for the preparation of some edibles for the children, sufficient protective food would be available at a very low cost. Basu and Basak (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 1043) have found that at 5% level of protein diets rice polishings from the Bengal variety of grains failed to produce growth on young rats, but maintenance was usually observed. On

the other hand Wan (*Chinese J. Physiol.*, 1935, 9, 140) made an attempt to process wheat bran for human consumption by soaking, steaming, frying and fermenting, and found that wheat bran could be utilised to the extent of 15 % in place of more refined cereal in an ordinary vegetarian diet. In a poor country like India, the possibilities of the utilisation of rice and wheat brans with their high nutritive values for human consumption, deserves more than a passing notice.

Regarding the iron content, at the present state of our knowledge, nothing need be said except that some of the unusually high figures are evidently due to handling those stuff with iron implements and utensils.

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